

THE CER FRAMEWORK INSTRUCTION AND THE ARGUMENTATIVE WRITING SKILLS OF GRADE 10 STUDENTS: A MEDIATION EFFECT

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ABSTRACT

Writing arguments is one of the competencies included in English language curriculum. It urgently requires improving students' argumentation skills for academic and professional achievement and democratic societies. In relation, this study sought to determine the effect of CER framework instruction in argumentative writing skills of grade 10 students in Dr. Panfilo Castro National High School. Specifically, it aimed to determine the significant difference between the pre-test and the post-test performance of the students on their argumentative writing skills in terms of comparison and contention, logic, and reason, and paragraph development and coherence. Fifty-one (51) respondents purposively selected and the study covered their first three weeks of third grading period in school year 2020-2021. It utilized an experimental design using single group pre-test-post-test design. The frequency, percentage distribution, and mean were used to determine the respondents' mean pre-test and post-test scores in the experimental study. One sample t-test was also utilized to determine the difference between the mean pre-test and post-test scores of the respondents. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that there is a significant difference between the pre – test and the post-test scores of the students on their argumentative writing skills. The study demonstrates that CER framework instruction allows students to more effectively convey their position, organize their ideas, and express the reasons using the framework. The researcher recommended that school administrators may conduct or provide a school – based workshop/ training on proper implementation of the CER as innovation to develop students' argumentative writing skills. Moreover, future researchers may study the effect of the CER framework instruction in other learning skills specifically the speaking skills or different academic types of writing skills.

Keywords: English Language, Argumentative Writing, CER Framework Instruction